

Created by Anjully Lozano
from Noun Project

CONTEXT

ASSETS

Created by Creative Stall
from Noun Project

DIGITAL RESOURCE

CONTEXT

ASSETS

LEARNING ACTIVITY

CONTEXT

ASSETS

Created by [AlfredoCreates.com/icons](https://alfredocreates.com/icons)
from Noun Project

OUTREACH ACTIVITY

CONTEXT

ASSETS

Created by Iulia Ardeleanu
from Noun Project

RETAIL

CONTEXT

ASSETS

Created by Made
from Noun Project

EXHIBITS

CONTEXT

ASSETS

Created by Wouter Buning
from Noun Project

CONTEXT

AUDIENCES

Created by Wouter Buning
from Noun Project

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from Noun Project

CONTEXT

AUDIENCES

INSTITUTIONAL

Created by Gan Khoon Lay
from Noun Project

ACCESSIBILITY

Almost 1 in 5 people are disabled. Physical accessibility to museums is improving but 27% of museum websites provide no information to help disabled visitors plan a visit and only 10% of museums provide audio descriptions and handling sessions for blind and partially-sighted visitors

DESIGN BRIEF

BARRIERS

Created by Andrejs Kirma
from Noun Project

OVERLOOKED GROUPS

A "traditional" approach to outreach may alienate a socially-isolated audience: museum activities overwhelmingly target schools and local friends groups, with little attention paid to disability, LGBTQ+, environmental and gender equality groups

DESIGN BRIEF

BARRIERS

Created by Gan Khoo Lay
from Noun Project

LACK OF SIGNAGE

Ineffective wayfinding signage and museum maps will frustrate the audience and limit the time they spend. Only 18% of museums publicise labels or information for their exhibits in large print, while the educational level required to understand the signage is often prohibitive

DESIGN BRIEF

BARRIERS

INSTITUTIONAL

Created by Pham Thi Dieu Linh
from Noun Project

IRRELEVANT ASSETS

Poor interpretation may prevent the visitor from drawing personal connections, or may reinforce negative stereotypes of the audience. The assets may represent a world-view at odds with that of the audience.

DESIGN BRIEF

BARRIERS

INSTITUTIONAL

Created by Adrien Coquet
from Noun Project

HIGH COST

Many museums are introducing or increasing entry prices, deterring an audience who live in degrees of poverty. Entry costs may also seem outdated in comparison to new charging models such as micro-payments, community ownership, and crowd-funding

DESIGN BRIEF

BARRIERS

INSTITUTIONAL

Created by Gan Khoon Lay
from Noun Project

DISCRIMINATION

Unconscious bias in museums influences staff recruitment, and decisions around programming, interpretation and representation in museum spaces, deterring potential volunteers and visitors who identify as diverse

DESIGN BRIEF

BARRIERS

Created by Till Teenck
from Noun Project

RESTRICTIVE OPENING HOURS

Opening hours may need to be adapted to fit an increasingly flexible and on-demand society. Some audiences may only be able to visit at night. Digital audiences may have different expectations of opening hours compared to physical visitors.

DESIGN BRIEF

BARRIERS

Created by anbilero adaleru
from the Noun Project

LACK OF ACCESS TO TECHNOLOGY

In 2017, 10% of households did not have access to the Internet. 24% of adults did not own a smartphone, and more than a quarter of those that do have a smartphone cannot access a 4G network

DESIGN BRIEF

BARRIERS

Created by David Alexander Slaager
from Noun Project

NO FIXED ABODE

In 2017 there were over 77,000 households without a fixed address, and over 4,000 people sleeping rough. Without a fixed address it may be impossible to register for membership, or access technologies such as telephones, computers and the Internet

DESIGN BRIEF

BARRIERS

Created by Chameleon Design
from Noun Project

LOW SELF ESTEEM

People with low self esteem may shy away from crowded venues and social situations, and avoid overtly challenging or provocative experiences

DESIGN BRIEF

BARRIERS

Created by Jenn_3D
from Noun Project

SOCIALLY ISOLATED

Social isolation can be caused physically through distance or disability, or emotionally through social stigmas. Isolation can be subjective, through a perceived lack of useful role in society. Isolation can make visits to heritage venues challenging or impossible

DESIGN BRIEF

BARRIERS

Created by Luis Prado
from Noun Project

POVERTY

One in five people live in "absolute poverty". Many more live in "relative poverty", struggling to pay for critical needs and curtailing access to non-essential cultural and leisure activities.

DESIGN BRIEF

BARRIERS

Created by Made by Made
from Noun Project

EDUCATIONALLY DISADVANTAGED

Less than half of the adult population has a qualification beyond an A-level. Educational experience affects how comfortable a visitor may be in critical or learning activities, and the perception of cultural venues as relevant

DESIGN BRIEF

BARRIERS

Created by Anton
from Noun Project

3D MODELLING

Visitor can use 3D scanning equipment, modelling software, and 3D printers to capture and produce physical assets

DESIGN BRIEF

CAPABILITIES

Created by Locad
from Noun Project

WEB DESIGN

Visitor can create and edit web content either using a content-management system or markup language

DESIGN BRIEF

CAPABILITIES

Created by Denis Shumaylov
from Noun Project

DIGITISATION

Visitor can use digitisation equipment
and software to turn physical resources
into digital resources

DESIGN BRIEF

CAPABILITIES

Created by Arslan Shahid
from Noun Project

MEDIA CREATION

Visitor can capture and prepare digital media, e.g. graphics, photos, audio and video

DESIGN BRIEF

CAPABILITIES

Created by Chameleon Design
from Noun Project

MIXED REALITY

Visitor can use augmented reality (AR) apps, or virtual reality (VR) headsets

DESIGN BRIEF

CAPABILITIES

Created by Chinnaking
from Noun Project

COMPUTER GAMING

Visitor can play computer or console
games

DESIGN BRIEF

CAPABILITIES

Created by Jemis mali
from Noun Project

COMPUTER SOFTWARE

Visitor can download, install and use
computer software

DESIGN BRIEF

CAPABILITIES

Created by Symbolon
from Noun Project

SOCIAL MEDIA NETWORKS

The visitor can use social media networks to contact friends, family and acquaintances, promote their likes and dislikes, and form an understanding of their community

DESIGN BRIEF

CAPABILITIES

Created by Aneeqe Ahmed
from Noun Project

MOBILE APPS

Visitor can find, install and use mobile apps

DESIGN BRIEF

CAPABILITIES

Created by Adrien Coquet
from Noun Project

WEBSITES

Visitor can find and use websites

DESIGN BRIEF

CAPABILITIES

Created by Will Adams
from Noun Project

3D PRINTER

Using a digital 3D model as a guide, a computer gradually builds a physical 3D replica that can safely be handled, and might be combined with other physical objects

DESIGN BRIEF

DEVICES

Created by Tomasz Pasternak
from Noun Project

GAMING CONSOLE

A computer designed specifically to allow one or more people to play computer games together.

DESIGN BRIEF

DEVICES

Created by Nikita Kozin
from Noun Project

AUGMENTED REALITY HEADSET

A display worn over the eyes so that the wearer "looks through" the display to see the world around them, but overlaid with digital information. Some AR headsets allow the user to insert their mobile phone and use this as the display

DESIGN BRIEF

DEVICES

Created by Willy Roda
from Noun Project

VIRTUAL REALITY SYSTEM

Head-mounted display, hand-held controllers and other body-mounted sensors and feedback devices, that give the user a sense of being present in a virtual environment rather than the real world

DESIGN BRIEF

DEVICES

Created by Astutik Icon
from Noun Project

DUMB PHONE

A telephone that can receive calls and SMS messages, but is not connected to the Internet

DESIGN BRIEF

DEVICES

Created by Andy Mc
from Noun Project

CAMERA

A dedicated device for capturing images
of people and the surroundings

DESIGN BRIEF

DEVICES

Created by i cons
from Noun Project

COMPUTER

A personal laptop or desktop computer,
now typically connected to the Internet

DESIGN BRIEF

DEVICES

Created by Gregor Cresnar
from Noun Project

TABLET

A portable computer with a touchscreen. More cumbersome than a smartphone, but offering a larger display that can possibly be shared by multiple users

DESIGN BRIEF

DEVICES

Created by icons.design
from Noun Project

SMART PHONE

A telephone that is connected to the Internet and GPS, and supports a range of apps that vastly extend its functionality. Importantly, it allows the users to create and share digital content

DESIGN BRIEF

DEVICES

Created by GreenHill
from Noun Project

HEALTH TRACKER

A wearable computer that monitors bodily functions, such as heart rate, and passes on the data to services that process it to give feedback or trigger alerts when appropriate

DESIGN BRIEF

DEVICES

Created by misirlou
from Noun Project

SMART WATCH

A computer worn on the wrist that provides a simple alternative to the functionality of a smartphone, giving access to mobile apps, information from the Web, and alerts

DESIGN BRIEF

DEVICES

EMOTIONAL

Created by Pravin Unagar
from Noun Project

CULTURAL IDENTITY

The visitor hopes to learn more about their cultural history and place in their community

DESIGN BRIEF

MOTIVATIONS

EMOTIONAL

Created by Pepper Curry
from Noun Project

NOSTALGIA

The museum represents a positive view of the recent past: good memories that can be relived during the visit

DESIGN BRIEF

MOTIVATIONS

EMOTIONAL

Created by Olena Panasovska
from Noun Project

EXPERIENCE THE PAST

The visitor enjoys travelling back in time to a experience a way of life that is unfamiliar but intriguing

DESIGN BRIEF

MOTIVATIONS

EMOTIONAL

Created by Symbolon
from Noun Project

PERSONAL RELEVANCE

The visitor is attracted by a personal connection that they share with the museum

DESIGN BRIEF

MOTIVATIONS

EMOTIONAL

Created by I Create Stuff
from Noun Project

TO BE MOVED

The visitor yearns for emotional stimulation - for the museum to provoke positive or negative arousal

DESIGN BRIEF

MOTIVATIONS

EMOTIONAL

Created by Pham Thi Dieu Linh
from Noun Project

AWE & WONDER

The visitor wants to be amazed by experiences that are incomprehensible, spectacular or surprising

DESIGN BRIEF

MOTIVATIONS

EMOTIONAL

Created by Royyan Wijaya
from Noun Project

AESTHETIC PLEASURE

The visitor responds on an emotional level to art and natural beauty, without the need to intellectualise the experience

DESIGN BRIEF

MOTIVATIONS

Created by Yeoul Kwon
from Noun Project

STIMULATE THE CHILDREN

The visitor is looking for a way to provide an education or otherwise positive influence for their children, or to simply share the burden of care

DESIGN BRIEF

MOTIVATIONS

INTELLECTUAL

Created by Daniel Falk
from Noun Project

SELF IMPROVEMENT

The visitor hopes to gain knowledge,
learn new skills, and become cultured

DESIGN BRIEF

MOTIVATIONS

INTELLECTUAL

Created by Fatemah Manji
from Noun Project

ACADEMIC INTEREST

The visitor has a critical interest in the assets of the museum, and is looking to develop a complete understanding of a topic and thus become an expert

DESIGN BRIEF

MOTIVATIONS

Created by Oksana Latysheva
from Noun Project

ACCESS, COMFORT & WARMTH

The visitor is looking for a safe space where they can feel "at home", possibly because they do not have a home or their home life is disturbed or harmful

DESIGN BRIEF

MOTIVATIONS

SOCIAL

Created by Alberto Miranda
from Noun Project

INCLUSION

The visitor is looking for a community to join, possibly to combat a feeling of social isolation or lack of cultural identity

DESIGN BRIEF

MOTIVATIONS

SOCIAL

Created by Lluisa Iborra
from Noun Project

TO MAKE & DO

The visitor enjoys being in a creative space where they can work with others to produce

DESIGN BRIEF

MOTIVATIONS

SOCIAL

Created by Blaise Sewell
from Noun Project

ENTERTAINMENT

The visitor enjoys being amused, intrigued and surprised by experts and standing back to witness a great show

DESIGN BRIEF

MOTIVATIONS

Created by Kirill Kolchenko
from Noun Project

SOCIAL INTERACTION

The museum provides an opportunity for dialogue and the company of others, which may be lacking elsewhere

DESIGN BRIEF

MOTIVATIONS

SPIRITUAL

Created by Andrew Doane
from Noun Project

STIMULATION

The visitor hopes to be deeply provoked by the experience and to be encouraged to reflect on their own beliefs and attitudes

DESIGN BRIEF

MOTIVATIONS

Created by Hyemm.work
from Noun Project

CONTEMPLATION

The museum provides a space to rationalise or consider, away from interruptions that might occur elsewhere

DESIGN BRIEF

MOTIVATIONS

SPIRITUAL

Created by Luis Prado
from Noun Project

ESCAPISM

The museum represents an alternative to everyday life - a place to have experiences that provide a pleasing contrast to their home or work

DESIGN BRIEF

MOTIVATIONS

CONTENT

Created by Gregor Cresnar
from Noun Project

INFINITE ARCHIVE

Will the experience create an overwhelming new collection to be maintained? Will you be able to devote the appropriate level of care to the collection as it grows? Are there plans in place to limit its size?

DISRUPTION

BEYOND

CONTENT

Created by Hare Krishna
from Noun Project

REPLAY

Does the experience provide value for a repeat visit? Is there a benefit to being an experienced visitor?

DISRUPTION

BEYOND

CONTENT

Created by Kirby Wu
from Noun Project

MODERATION

How will you control visitor contributions? Do you need to and, if yes, do you have the resource?

DISRUPTION

BEYOND

CONTENT

Created by Heiko Maiwand
from Noun Project

SHELF LIFE

How long will your content remain relevant? Can you add new content over time?

DISRUPTION

BEYOND

Created by beth bolton
from Noun Project

MY CONTENT

Will visitors create and/or contribute content? Is there a licensing agreement in place to allow you to use it legally?

DISRUPTION

BEYOND

Created by Ellricon
from Noun Project

MY DATA

Will you collect any information that can be linked to a visitor? Can you easily give this data back to the visitor and delete it if they ask?

DISRUPTION

BEYOND

LEGAL

Created by Giuditta Valentina Gentile
from Noun Project

THEIR CONTENT

Will you collect and/or process content
from other platforms, e.g. social media?
Are you abiding by their terms of use?

DISRUPTION

BEYOND

Created by Ben Davis
from Noun Project

SCALABILITY

If the experience becomes very popular can the venue, staff and technology handle an increasing audience? When will capacity become a problem? Are limiting mechanisms needed? Can you scale down if popularity is sporadic?

DISRUPTION

BEYOND

Created by H Y P E R M O R G E N
from Noun Project

REPLICABILITY

If it is effective, does the experience have wider applicability? Can the experience be repeated at other venues or applied to other assets and audiences? Or is it limited in scope?

DISRUPTION

BEYOND

RESOURCE

Created by Arafat Uddin
from Noun Project

RELIANCE

Are particular volunteers or staff vital for the experience? What happens if they leave?

DISRUPTION

BEYOND

RESOURCE

Created by Vectors Market
from Noun Project

FUNDING

Does the experience rely on funding?
How long will that funding last?

DISRUPTION

BEYOND

Created by Gan Khoon Lay
from Noun Project

BIG CHALLENGES

Does the experience relate to or help tackle local societal issues? How about national or global issues?

DISRUPTION

BEYOND

Created by Gregor Cresnar
from Noun Project

SOCIAL NETWORK

How will you understand and engage
with opinion on social networks?

DISRUPTION

BEYOND

TECHNOLOGY

Created by Dairy Free Design
from Noun Project

FASHION

Is the popularity of technology underpinning the experience being driven by trend-setters? If it is "on-trend" now, have you planned for the day the trend changes?

DISRUPTION

BEYOND

Created by Gan Khoon Lay
from Noun Project

RESPONSIBILITY

Is there a person or people with ultimate responsibility for the experience? Will they continuously improve and evaluate it?

DISRUPTION

BEYOND

Created by Wilson Joseph
from Noun Project

MAINTENANCE

Does your staff have the expertise for day-to-day maintenance of the technology? Is there someone on hand to tackle small problems?

DISRUPTION

BEYOND

TECHNOLOGY

Created by Gregor Cresnar
from Noun Project

SUPPORT

Will the technology be around in a year's time? How about 5 years? How long can you expect external support?

DISRUPTION

BEYOND

Created by SBTS
from Noun Project

ENERGY USE

How much energy is consumed? Has this cost been accounted for?

DISRUPTION

BEYOND

VENUE

Created by Nikita Kozin
from Noun Project

RELOCATION

Will the venue always be available? Can the experience be relocated or taken indoors/outdoors?

DISRUPTION

BEYOND

BEHAVIOUR

Created by Sierra Pennala
from Noun Project

FLOW

Are there established patterns/trajectories of visitor movement? Can these be changed?

DISRUPTION

CONSTRAINTS

ENVIRONMENT

Created by corpus delicti
from Noun Project

POLITICS & POLICIES

Will this experience clash with the museum's policies, its politics, or general philosophy? If so, is this a problem?

DISRUPTION

CONSTRAINTS

ENVIRONMENT

Created by Yu luck
from Noun Project

DISTRACTION

Is the venue an inherently noisy or otherwise distracting environment?

DISRUPTION

CONSTRAINTS

ENVIRONMENT

Created by Gan Khoon Lay
from Noun Project

PEACE

Do visitors expect a calm, contemplative atmosphere? Can this be broken?

DISRUPTION

CONSTRAINTS

LOCATION

Created by icon 54
from Noun Project

SAFE SPACE

Is there a space where visitors can assemble and plan before the experience, or take a rest and reflect afterwards?

DISRUPTION

CONSTRAINTS

LOCATION

Created by Made
from Noun Project

LEGIBILITY

Is it easy for visitors to identify and navigate to different parts of the venue? Will they be able to find their way during the experience?

DISRUPTION

CONSTRAINTS

LOCATION

Created by Parma
from Noun Project

CAPACITY

How much space is available for the visit? Should there be more or less?

DISRUPTION

CONSTRAINTS

LOCATION

Created by Jordan Delcros
from Noun Project

ACCESSIBILITY

Does the venue cater for visitors of all physical abilities? If not, can visitors still engage somehow?

DISRUPTION

CONSTRAINTS

LOCATION

Created by Vitor Alexandre Ferreira
from Noun Project

DYNAMIC SPACES

Will the locations stay accessible and unchanged? Will they need to be shared?

DISRUPTION

CONSTRAINTS

RESOURCES

Created by Nikita Kozin
from Noun Project

RISK

Do you have staff with experience of conducting risk assessments for this type of experience? Do you have liability insurance to cover the risks encountered during the experience?

DISRUPTION

CONSTRAINTS

RESOURCES

Created by icon 54
from Noun Project

UNSTABLE CONNECTIVITY

Is wifi and/or phone signal necessary for the experience? Is it available and dependable?

DISRUPTION

CONSTRAINTS

RESOURCES

Created by Rose Duong
from Noun Project

REDUNDANT GUIDES

Do staff or volunteers guide visitors?
Could the new experience alter or
replace this role?

DISRUPTION

CONSTRAINTS

RESOURCES

Created by Tori Lewis
from Noun Project

CONSERVATION

Are there objects or locations that need protection? How can you keep them safe during the experience?

DISRUPTION

CONSTRAINTS

Created by Andy Houghton
from Noun Project

HUMAN RESOURCE

Does the experience change based on available staff or volunteers? When might this happen, and what will the consequences be?

DISRUPTION

EXPERIENCE

ENVIRONMENT

Created by Llisole
from Noun Project

DISTRACTION

Do visitors create a lot of noise or behave in a way that might interfere with other visitors?

DISRUPTION

EXPERIENCE

ENVIRONMENT

Created by Patrick Morrison
from Noun Project

WEATHER

How will changes in the weather affect the experience?

DISRUPTION

EXPERIENCE

ETHICS

Created by Ed Piel
from Noun Project

MINORS

Does your experience rely on children providing personal information or creating content? If so, have you ensured that an appropriate adult has helped them to provide informed consent? Do children interact with staff or other visitors? If so, this should happen under the supervision of an appropriate adult

DISRUPTION

EXPERIENCE

Created by Luis Prado
from Noun Project

UNCOMFORTABLE INTERACTIONS

Will the visitor be embarrassed or otherwise uncomfortable during the experience? Is this necessary? Can they avoid the uncomfortable situation?

DISRUPTION

EXPERIENCE

CONSENT

Are you collecting any information that can be linked to a visitor? Has the visitor given fully informed consent?

DISRUPTION

EXPERIENCE

ETHICS

Created by Jessica Lock
from Noun Project

ABUSE

Does the experience make it more likely or encourage visitors to cause offence or break the law?

DISRUPTION

EXPERIENCE

Created by [iconsmind.com](https://www.iconsmind.com)
from Noun Project

DATA BLOAT

Is data being captured without a clear reason or strategy for processing it? This may contravene new data protection regulations, but also adds unnecessary cost and complexity to data infrastructure

DISRUPTION

EXPERIENCE

Created by JMA
from Noun Project

BATTERY LIFE

Does the experience drain the visitor's devices of energy? Will the batteries last?

DISRUPTION

EXPERIENCE

Created by Maria Kislitsina
from Noun Project

FOCUS OF ATTENTION

Will visitors be staring at their screens
rather than their surroundings?

DISRUPTION

EXPERIENCE

TECHNOLOGY

Created by emilegraphics
from Noun Project

COMPLEX

Is too much technology involved in the experience? Can it be done with less tech?

DISRUPTION

EXPERIENCE

TRAJECTORY

Created by Creative Stall
from Noun Project

EXHAUSTION

Is the experience physically tiring? Is it mentally tiring? Is this necessary and, if so, is there room to rest?

DISRUPTION

EXPERIENCE

TRAJECTORY

Created by Jems Mayor
from Noun Project

NARRATIVE

What story does the visit tell? Does it have a satisfying beginning and end? Does the visitor need to experience the elements in a particular order?

DISRUPTION

EXPERIENCE

TRAJECTORY

Created by Jhun Capaya
from Noun Project

AT A GLANCE

Will visitors understand what to do if they pay little attention to the instructions?

DISRUPTION

EXPERIENCE

TRAJECTORY

Created by priyanka
from Noun Project

CRITICAL MASS

Does there need to be a particular number of visitors for the experience to work?

DISRUPTION

EXPERIENCE

Created by Dilla Chee
from Noun Project

CONFIGURATION

Does the experience work for single visitors and groups? Couples and tour groups? School groups?

DISRUPTION

EXPERIENCE

TRAJECTORY

Created by Martyn Jasinski
from Noun Project

PACE

Will members of a group interact at their own pace? What happens to the group if they do?

DISRUPTION

EXPERIENCE

TRAJECTORY

Created by Alberto Alonso
from Noun Project

INVESTMENT

Will visitors spend as much time as you hope? What if they don't?

DISRUPTION

EXPERIENCE

TRAJECTORY

Created by Creative Mania
from Noun Project

RULES

Are visitors told what to do? Is it reasonable to expect visitors to follow those rules?

DISRUPTION

EXPERIENCE

VALUE

Created by Gan Khoo Lay
from Noun Project

BUZZ

Will the visitor have something to tell their friends, family, acquaintances or other potential visitors? Can you help them do this?

DISRUPTION

EXPERIENCE

VALUE

Created by Ryan Dell
from Noun Project

BIGGER PICTURE

Does the new experience enhance other elements of the visit, and the broader relationship with the museum?

DISRUPTION

EXPERIENCE

VALUE

Created by Dairy Free Design
from Noun Project

PROVOCATION

How challenging is the visit? How fun?
How provocative?

DISRUPTION

EXPERIENCE

VALUE

Created by Amrit Mazumder
from Noun Project

ENGAGEMENT

Do visitors actively engage with the museum, or remain passive? Do they leave having begun a relationship with the museum?

DISRUPTION

EXPERIENCE

LOCATION

Created by misirlou
from Noun Project

OFFLINE

The visitor is taken to a location where there is no wifi, phone signal or GPS

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

LOCATION

Created by Aneeqe Ahmed
from Noun Project

OUTDOORS

Visitors leave the venue, school, office,
home or any other buildings

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

LOCATION

Created by Musmellow
from Noun Project

ONLINE

Part (or all) of the visit takes place online, whether this is on a website, social network, or elsewhere

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

LOCATION

Created by BomSymbols
from Noun Project

TRANSPORT

Part (or all) of the visit takes place while the visitor is travelling

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

LOCATION

Created by Ralf Schmitzer
from Noun Project

ANYWHERE

The visitor can be involved wherever they are, although the experience might vary

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

LOCATION

Created by Gabriele Debolini
from Noun Project

HOPPING

The visitor must travel between
locations or venues

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

LOCATION

Created by Roberto Notarangelo
from Noun Project

FITTING LOCATIONS

The atmosphere of the location
supports the visit

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

LOCATION

Created by Gan Khoon Lay
from Noun Project

SUBVERTED LOCATIONS

Visitor behaves in ways that are
unexpected/contravene the location

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

LOCATION

Created by Alex Tai
from Noun Project

HIDDEN LOCATIONS

Visitors get to visit places they
otherwise would not

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

MECHANIC

Created by Vectors Market
from Noun Project

CHECK-IN

The visitor arrives at exhibits, places or events and announces (to the museum or other visitors) that they have done so

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

MECHANIC

Created by Gan Khoon Lay
from Noun Project

CACHES

Visitors follow instructions to find hiding places, and use them to pass on objects or content to other visitors

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

MECHANIC

Created by parkjsun
from Noun Project

VOLUNTEERS

Visitors take on the responsibility of a member of staff

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

MECHANIC

Created by Gan Khoon Lay
from Noun Project

MOB

Personal instructions cause visitors to gather together at a particular place and time

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

MECHANIC

Created by Dan Hetteix
from Noun Project

GATEKEEPERS

Visitors induct other people into the
experience

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

MECHANIC

Created by Yu luck
from Noun Project

CROWD-SOURCING

The visitor carries out a short, simple task to help solve a more complex issue

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

MECHANIC

Created by Hyemm.work
from Noun Project

STORYTELLING

The visitor creates or adds to a public narrative

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

MECHANIC

Created by Rflor
from Noun Project

Q&A

The visitor asks questions and receives answers from staff, volunteers or other visitors

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

MECHANIC

Created by Gan Khoo Lay
from Noun Project

ADOPTION

The visitor takes on the role of caretaker
or curator of an asset

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

MECHANIC

Created by IQON
from Noun Project

MARKETPLACE

The visitor creates and trades their content with other visitors or the venue

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

MECHANIC

Created by Made by Made
from Noun Project

CITIZEN SCIENCE

The visitor plays an active role in the museum's research using their own technology

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

MECHANIC

Created by Jon Testa
from Noun Project

EPIISODES

Exhibits, content and story are divided into parts and revealed over time or multiple visits

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

MECHANIC

Created by CINDYFLA
from Noun Project

SEAMFUL DESIGN

Technical (or other) flaws are embraced
as positive elements of the visit

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

MECHANIC

Created by Krisada
from Noun Project

GIFTING

Visitors create meaningful content and exchange it with each other

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

MECHANIC

Created by Chris Homan
from Noun Project

APPOINTMENT

The visitor needs to be at a particular place (at a particular time)

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

MECHANIC

Created by Gregor Cresnar
from Noun Project

DECISION

The visitor must make a choice that
affects their subsequent experience

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

BEGINNING & END

The experience has a start and end that frame the visit

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

MECHANIC

Created by Gregor Cresnar
from Noun Project

INVITE IMITATION

The visitor is given the skills and tools to act as an expert

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

MECHANIC

Created by Delwar Hossain
from Noun Project

CRITICISM

The progress of the visitor is evaluated
and reflected back

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

MECHANIC

Created by Michael Wohlwend
from Noun Project

PERSONA

The visitor constructs or adopts a character during the visit

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

MECHANIC

COLLECT

The visitor builds a personal collection of content and/or achievements

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

MECHANIC

Created by Bastien Delmare
from Noun Project

REWARD

The visitor is rewarded as they complete challenges during the visit

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

MECHANIC

Created by Creative Stall
from Noun Project

PRESSURE

Each visit has a fixed duration or scope

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

PHYSICAL

Created by Strokeicon
from Noun Project

GESTURES

The visitor makes movements or signs with their body to trigger a reaction

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

PHYSICAL

HACKING & CRAFTING

The visitor creates new physical objects

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

PHYSICAL

Created by davidyu
from Noun Project

HANDS ON

The visitor can touch and use physical assets

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

PHYSICAL

LOW TECH

The visitor uses old-fashioned but reliable technology

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

PHYSICAL

Created by Fabio Rinaldi
from Noun Project

TECHNICAL ARTIFACTS

Mundane objects are made
(unexpectedly) interactive by adding
technology

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

SENSORY

Created by Pham Thi Dieu Linh
from Noun Project

BIO-SENSING

Health trackers or other physiological sensors record the visitor's physical reactions

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

SENSORY

Created by Julien Deveaux
from Noun Project

AUTHENTICITY

Sight, sound, smell and touch are augmented to give an "authentic" experience

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

SENSORY

Created by Manuel Nilsson
from Noun Project

MOTION TRACKING

Sensors measure visitor orientation,
gestures and/or movement

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

SENSORY

Created by Alina Oleynik
from Noun Project

HAPTIC FEEDBACK

Physical feedback is delivered to the visitor's body based on their location and progress

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

SENSORY

Created by Anastasia Latysheva
from Noun Project

PERSONAL SOUNDTRACK

Music and sounds change based on the
location and progress of visitors

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

SOCIAL

Created by parkjsun
from Noun Project

OUTREACH

Staff go to the visitors, and work to directly impact their community

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

SOCIAL

Created by Thengakola
from Noun Project

NEW ACQUAINTANCES

Unfamiliar visitors meet each other

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

SOCIAL

Created by Icondesk
from Noun Project

NETWORKED

Visitors in the venue communicate with people outside the venue

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

SOCIAL

Created by Creative Mania
from Noun Project

COMPETITION

Visitors must compete with each other

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

SOCIAL

Created by abeldb
from Noun Project

COLLABORATION

Visitors must work with each other

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

SOCIAL

Created by Aldric Rodríguez
from Noun Project

BLURRED BOUNDARIES

Visitors engage directly with non-visitors

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

TECHNOLOGY

Created by Veremeya
from Noun Project

PAPER

The visitor writes or draws on paper as
a way of creating content

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

Created by Piotrek Chuchla
from Noun Project

PROJECTION

The environment around the visitor is enhanced with visual projections.

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

TECHNOLOGY

Created by shashank singh
from Noun Project

VIDEO

The visitor captures and manipulates
video

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

TECHNOLOGY

Created by ArtWorkLeaf
from Noun Project

AUDIO

The visitor captures and manipulates
voice or other sounds

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

Created by Creative Stall
from Noun Project

2D SCANNING

The visitor creates a digital copy of a document, artwork or other flat media

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

3D PRINTING

The visitor creates a physical reproduction of a 3D digital model

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

Created by sandra
from Noun Project

3D SCANNING

The visitor creates a digital reproduction
of a physical object

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

Created by Mooms
from Noun Project

VIRTUAL REALITY

The visitor enters an immersive virtual environment that temporarily replaces the real world

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

Created by Delwar Hossain
from Noun Project

BIOMETRICS

The visitor's physical characteristics are recorded and used as a trigger

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

TECHNOLOGY

Created by Adnen Kadri
from Noun Project

PHOTOGRAPHY

Visitors stage, take and manipulate photos

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

Created by Rflor
from Noun Project

INSTANT MESSAGING

Visitors send and/or receive instant
messages

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

Created by Gregor Cresnar
from Noun Project

INTELLIGENT ASSISTANT

The visitor can ask questions or otherwise interact with an automated expert system

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

Created by Alvaro Cabrera
from Noun Project

LINKED DATA

Your assets are linked to open information held across the web, allowing visitors to freely browse that content

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

TECHNOLOGY

Created by Aneeqe Ahmed
from Noun Project

SHOP

The visitor can buy digital content from
an online or virtual shop

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

VISUAL MARKERS

Visitors scan objects to reveal hidden information or trigger an event

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

TECHNOLOGY

Created by Stéphanie Rusch
from Noun Project

PROXIMITY

Sensors detect nearby visitors and react when they are close or touching

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

Created by Ilya Kolbin
from Noun Project

PUBLIC DISPLAYS

Small or big screens, situated in the environment, play a role in the visit

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

Created by Joris Hoogendoorn
from Noun Project

SOCIAL MEDIA

Visitors create opinions and other content, and share it publicly

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

TECHNOLOGY

Created by Océan Bussard
from Noun Project

TELEPHONY

Visitors make and/or receive phone calls or text messages

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

Created by Evangeline La
from Noun Project

AUGMENTED REALITY

The visitor views digital content overlaid
into the surrounding environment

IDEATION

BUILDING BLOCKS

ASSETS

Created by Maxim Basinski
from Noun Project

INCREASE EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES

INSTITUTIONAL GOALS

GOALS

ASSETS

Created by Creative Stall
from Noun Project

USE ASSETS IN NEW WAYS

INSTITUTIONAL GOALS

GOALS

ASSETS

Created by Wilson Joseph
from Noun Project

USE GREATER PROPORTION OF ASSETS

INSTITUTIONAL GOALS

GOALS

ASSETS

Created by Hussain Khalil
from Noun Project

DIGITISE MORE ASSETS

INSTITUTIONAL GOALS

GOALS

ASSETS

Created by H Alberto Gongora
from Noun Project

ACQUIRE MORE DIVERSE ASSETS

INSTITUTIONAL GOALS

GOALS

AWARENESS

Created by Becris
from Noun Project

INCREASE VISITOR FEEDBACK

INSTITUTIONAL GOALS

GOALS

AWARENESS

Created by Presenttas
from Noun Project

GREATER BRAND AWARENESS

INSTITUTIONAL GOALS

GOALS

AWARENESS

Created by Becris
from Noun Project

HIGHER VISITOR SATISFACTION

INSTITUTIONAL GOALS

GOALS

AWARENESS

Created by Juan Pablo Bravo
from Noun Project

MORE VISITOR AMBASSADORS

INSTITUTIONAL GOALS

GOALS

AWARENESS

Created by Symbolon
from Noun Project

WIDER SOCIAL MEDIA DIVERSITY

INSTITUTIONAL GOALS

GOALS

AWARENESS

Created by Björn Andersson
from Noun Project

FURTHER SOCIAL MEDIA REACH

INSTITUTIONAL GOALS

GOALS

ENGAGEMENT

Created by Drishya
from Noun Project

INCREASE OUTREACH

INSTITUTIONAL GOALS

GOALS

ENGAGEMENT

Created by Yu luck
from Noun Project

INCREASE VISITOR PARTICIPATION

INSTITUTIONAL GOALS

GOALS

ENGAGEMENT

Created by YuguDesign
from Noun Project

INCREASE VOLUNTEERING

INSTITUTIONAL GOALS

GOALS

ENGAGEMENT

Created by Dinosoft Labs
from Noun Project

INCREASE ONLINE VISITS

INSTITUTIONAL GOALS

GOALS

ENGAGEMENT

Created by Laymik
from Noun Project

INCREASE VISIT DURATION

INSTITUTIONAL GOALS

GOALS

HOW MANY?

Created by Llisole
from Noun Project

INCREASE REPEAT VISITS

INSTITUTIONAL GOALS

GOALS

HOW MANY?

Created by Deepak M
from Noun Project

INCREASE VISITOR NUMBERS

INSTITUTIONAL GOALS

GOALS

HOW MANY?

Created by Niels Gesquiere
from Noun Project

INCREASE MEMBERSHIP

INSTITUTIONAL GOALS

GOALS

HOW MANY?

Created by Shuaibu Usman Yusuf
from Noun Project

**INCREASE
DONATIONS**

INSTITUTIONAL GOALS

GOALS

HOW MANY?

Created by Adrien Coquet
from Noun Project

INCREASE VISITOR SPEND

INSTITUTIONAL GOALS

GOALS

SUSTAINABILITY

Created by Sarah JOY
from Noun Project

WIN MORE FUNDING

INSTITUTIONAL GOALS

GOALS

Created by Aneeqe Ahmed
from Noun Project

MORE DATA-DRIVEN DECISIONS

INSTITUTIONAL GOALS

GOALS

SUSTAINABILITY

Created by Nikita Kozin
from Noun Project

REDUCE VENUE COSTS

INSTITUTIONAL GOALS

GOALS

WHO?

Created by Vectors Market
from Noun Project

INCREASE INTERNATIONAL REACH

INSTITUTIONAL GOALS

GOALS

WHO?

Created by S Madsen
from Noun Project

ATTRACT NEW DEMOGRAPHICS

INSTITUTIONAL GOALS

GOALS

WHO?

Created by IconDots
from Noun Project

CHANGE VISITING PARTY SIZE

INSTITUTIONAL GOALS

GOALS

WHO?

Created by Luis Prado
from Noun Project

CHANGE VISITOR ATTITUDES OR BELIEFS

INSTITUTIONAL GOALS

GOALS

INFO

VISITORBOX

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